

5G Security

Drivers, Challenges and Opportunities

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Overview

- 5G Security Drivers
- 4G to 5G Security Evolution
- 5G security Challenges and Opportunities

5G Security Drivers

- Pressure from Business and Regulatory stakeholders
 - Digitalisation, supply chains,
 - Liability, reputation, trust-building
- User Privacy awareness
- 5G is about (enabler of) Use Cases, supporting new type of devices and business models -> new trust model
- New service delivery model
- Attack surface grows with 5G
 - IoT devices
 - Virtualisation and cloud-delivery (SBA, network-slicing)
 - Secure software, shared resource
- Criminal activities
 - 0.8% of global GDP (ca. 600 B yearly)
 - 5G opens more „opportunities“ to criminals

Need for measurable security and compliance, privacy safeguarding

4G to 5G Evolution

- 3GPP SA3 is the working group that develops mobile communications security specifications

4G Security Architecture

Evolution of 4G Security

Potential Threats of 4G

- IMSI in clear
- Temporary identity not changed
- No UP integrity protection
- Bid-down to GSM

Interconnect threats due to SS7 & Diameter

3GPP 5G Specification Phases

5G Phase 1 Security - Overview

5G Security Functions

SBA and Network Slicing bring cloud and NFV to the mobile network service

Virtualisation Security

Threats

- Data manipulation
- Privilege misuse
- Package modification
- Rogue VNF
- Malicious code or tenant
- Configuration modification
- Resource allocation issues
- Image tampering
- Catalogue information exploit
- Uploading malicious images

Mitigation

- Secure boot and chain of trust
- Remote attestation
- Secure crash
- Security assurance, signing and verification of image
- VNF isolation
- Tenant and administrator isolation

5G Security Next Steps

- Phase 2
 - Long-term key update
 - 256 bits keys usage
 - Security Assurance
 - Network Slicing Security
 - Location services Security
 - Security for URLLC
 - Security for Vertical & LAN Services

Holistic Security

- Security by Design
- Zero Trust

Opportunities - Targets

- Service Providers (Mobile NS-Operators, IT, Digitalisation – IoT, verticals)
 - Understand own connectivity and security requirements
 - Map the requirements to 5G and virtualisation (delivery model)
 - Develop appropriate security management and increase degree of automation
- Vendors
 - Implement as cloud-native
 - Security assurance tests as specified by 3GPP
 - Adapt to customer network architecture and changes

Opportunities

- Security Assurance as a Service

- **Objective:** provide a customer-tailored security solution for the customer enterprise application- and network-services
 - Implement the customer-defined security policies
 - Provide security visibility and integrate with the customer Security Operations Center
 - Provide regulatory compliance and Lawful Interception
 - Integrate / Interoperate with the enterprise application- and network-Service Providers

No specific security knowledge required from the app and connectivity DevOps

Opportunities

- Security Assurance as a Service

- Challenges:

- IAM :

- Interoperability / federation with CSP-domains (mediated by local Orchestrators) and legacy on-premise,
 - flexible authentication and authorization by means of dynamic configuration of IAM- components triggered by the customer security policy
 - Key Management and secure store
 - Traffic visibility / duplication: middlebox security protocols

Thank You!

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